

Searching the Great Metadata Timeline: A Review of Library Metadata Standards from Linear Cataloguing rules to Ontology inspired Metadata Standards

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Abstract:

Purpose: The purpose of this paper is to make a systematic review of the library metadata development history listing out the most significant landmarks and influencing events from Thomas Bodley's rules to the latest BIBFRAME architecture, compare their significance and suitability in the modern-day web environment.

Design/Methodology/Approach: Four-time divisions were identified *viz.* pre-1900 era, 1900 to 1950, Post 1950 to Pre-Web era and Post-Web era based on pre-set information available to the authors regarding catalogue rules. Under these four divisions, relevant information sources regarding the purpose of the study were identified; various metadata standards released at different times were consulted.

Findings: Library catalogue standards have undergone transitive changes from one form to another primarily influenced by the changing work environment and different forms of resource availability in libraries. Modern-day metadata standards are influenced by the opportunities provided by the World Wide Web towards libraries and works as a suitable base for data organisation at par with semantic web standards.

Research Limitation/Implications: Information organisation processes have gone towards a more data-centric approach than earlier document-centric nature in today's semantic web environment. Libraries had to make a move in this process, and modern-day guidelines in this regard bring the possibility of large scale discovery services through curated information resources.

Originality/value: The study discovers relationships between key events in the course of development of metadata standards and provides suggestions and predictions regarding its future developments.

Paper type: Review

Keywords: Metadata, Ontology, Metadata History, Library Cataloguing, Linked Data

1 Introduction:

Metadata for libraries is a first-class object, and it is used in libraries not only to describe a resource but also to connect a resource to other resources (Powell & Hopkins, 2016). Library catalogues are an essential part of the knowledge organisation process in a library, and an interactive catalogue is essential for providing multiple access points to various library holdings. Especially with the web technology, various forms of a single resource are available in multiple locations and data of catalogues can be made more inclusive by linking with other significant resources of similar entities, creating a broad base for highly valuable community resources. For example, if the catalogue entry of a book about the "Mourya dynasty of India" is connected with the museum and other artefact details of the Mouryas available on the web, then the catalogue will be more intuitive. Integration of data elements about similar objects

will add semantic flavour to the catalogues. Cataloguing standards have already been subjected to many changes because of the changes in resources and library management procedures as libraries cannot have an excuse for not being able to provide information about objects not part of its holdings (Chandel & Prasad, 2013). The semantic web facilitates libraries to go for better information processing and linking of objects in a precise manner. Libraries traditionally have a very highly structured data, but these data currently have limited usefulness to specific user-oriented services only but not to the whole web. With the emergence of the philosophy of the semantic web, library catalogues can be an essential part of the artificial intelligence-enabled web. Ontologies are thought to play the same role in the semantic web, what catalogues played for libraries. Ontology is a concept under the semantic web, that underlines associated logical meanings among metadata concept (Gruber, 1993). Ontology and metadata are two different entities. Their application is to make data uniformly structured, easily understandable and sharable across platforms. Even though their applicability is the same, but there is a thin line of difference between them, which makes them two different entities. Historically the term metadata was coined by American computer scientist Philip Bagley (Norman, 2019) in 1968. However, libraries have always been using metadata as rules for storing information as an index to the document collection. Metadata dates back to the pre-computer era, whereas Ontology is a concept of the post-World Wide Web era. Metadata is an essential part of database-backed electronic information storage, while ontology is indispensable to semantic web-based applications. Metadata consisted of a shared accepted vocabulary for information description, but ontologies tried to provide the model of knowledge in a domain by adding shared semantic to metadata. With changes that have been coming up in the World Wide Web era, libraries have also been going through the associated reforms, and so does library metadata standards.

The current study is a systematic review of the history and development of the library metadata standards from the 19th century to its current form and analyses the effect of web technology in the forms of library metadata. The study also analyses the modern cataloguing rules from the context of the semantic web structure. The paper has been designed into the following sections for a better interpretation of the review. Section 2 describes about conceptualisation of metadata in libraries; Section 3 which further have been divided into some subsections incorporates the journey of library catalogue rules to its modern-day form; Section 4 does a sum up of the review explaining the landmarks of metadata timeline; Section 5 describes the modern-day semantic web philosophy and tries to bridge up the philosophy with modern library metadata schemes; Section 6 incorporates the findings and conclusions.

2 Metadata as conceptualised in libraries:

Classification and standardisation of information objects have always been an interest for library enthusiasts. Libraries have been traditionally involved in storing documents of different forms on different knowledge domains and in this task, libraries have been following some recorded rules. These rules were meant for uniform storing of documents so that when required, they can be easily retrieved. The uniform storing rules were embodied in some cards or in book form, which contains all the details about a library's holdings. These are called as the catalogues of libraries. Metadata idea is applied to different fields, but for libraries, it primarily conceives to book catalogue preparation.

Library catalogues metadata have two prime purposes- i) Identification of contents, ii) Collocation. For identification, libraries use information such as author name, title, publisher which are readily available in the item to be catalogued. For collocation, the information items used are the language of the book, subject headings list, storage location, etc., which are supplied from some authorized values accepted across libraries.

One common definition of metadata is "Data about data". The International Federation of Library Association (IFLA, 2018) defines metadata as "*Structured information used to describe information resources/objects for a variety of purposes.*"

American Library Association (ALA, 2018) describes metadata as “*information about other data*”, and the other data for libraries mean information object -like a book, film or government document.

Metadata are peculiar identity elements about objects, which isolates two similar objects from one another. Libraries have been using metadata in Library Management Systems (LMS) as a tool to index the documents.

Metadata like author name, book title, subject of the book, size, the language of the book are essential elements to fulfil the perspectives of information needs of a reader. Catalogue code means about some shared, agreed rules among libraries in the catalogue preparation process, so that uniformity is achieved in catalogues across libraries. Library systems before the development of any catalogue codes were using local codes stratified differently across different institutions. It was a big problem for shared bibliographic control, staff training and foremost the users not accustomed to different entry types in catalogue cards.

3 Review of the history of cataloguing rules:

The review attempt in the study has been made based on four-time divisions which were chosen based on a preset assumption about the cataloguing rule development history. The time divisions chosen for conducting the review were: The Pre-1900 era of cataloguing, 1900 to 1950 era of cataloguing, 1950 to Pre-web era of Cataloguing, and Cataloguing Post World Wide Web era. This categorization of time phases was highly influenced by already available information about the landmarks of the cataloguing history.

3.1 Pre-1900 era:

The primary function of library catalogue as described by C A Cutter (1876) in his *Rules for a Printed Dictionary Catalogue* is to assist a reader finding book by author, title or subject, showcasing a library's collection on a subject, on a given author and assisting the choice of reading based on edition or character. The early-stage development in the cataloguing history was actually for a written cataloguing standard. The history of catalogue finds its roots in the Library of Alexandria by Zenodatus where there used to be a small strip of paper attached with books containing author name, book title. There exist shreds of evidence (Casson, 2002) of catalogue uses in libraries of the ancient world, but these were only based on their localised systems. The theories of systematic organisation of libraries developed by Ganriel Naude & John Dury were meant for a code of conduct in library management and also argued for standard catalogue codes (Lerner, 1998). The earliest development of catalogue standard is hard to trace, but one of the most recognised earliest milestones in this regard (Frost, 1976) is Sir Thomas Bodley's rule of catalogue in the Oxford University Library in 1674. Also, as a result of the French revolution, the French government released a national code (Joseph, 1991) of library catalogue in 1791. The most prominent and most renowned landmark in this regard came from Sir Anthonio Panizi when he introduced the 91 rules for cataloguing printed books at the British Museum (Lubetzky, 2001). The rules were accepted by British Museum in 1839, later published (Blake, 2002) in 1841 as “Rules for the Compilation of the Catalogue”. Dramatic improvements were observed in the catalogues of the British museum after Panizi's rule (Norman, 2018). Panizi's rule gave very high emphasis on the author names and the alphabetical listing of catalogue cards. Esdaile regarded Panizi's rule as the first thorough code in library catalogue history (Sood, 2015).

Panizi's rule inspired American librarians to thought for adopting a written rule that can govern the catalogue preparation process. Charles C. Jewett (1853) of Smithsonian Institute introduced a modified 39 rule for cataloguing based on Panizi's rule, and it was publicly published in 1853 as *Smithsonian Catalogue System*. The Jewett system (Jewett, 1853) advocated for alphabetical catalogue cards, and it became a model for many libraries of that time (Mason, 2015). Jewett (1853) also wished for union catalogues among libraries and

proposed “*stereotype plates, a series of preserved, mass-produced separate titles to be composed in adherence to a set of stringent rules.*”

C A Cutter’s ***Rule for Dictionary Catalog*** is considered as the biggest of all landmarks in the 19th-century cataloguing rule development history. Cutter’s rules (1876) emphasised elaborately about the importance of catalogues in libraries and basic principles of it. Alternate entry for authors, titles, subjects and form headings were an essential part of Cutter’s rule, and because of its descriptive nature, it became so much popular. Later three revised editions of it were published in 1889, 1891 and 1904.

The rules of Panizi, Jewett and Cutter were fruitful for English speaking countries, but there were significant rules developed for the Libraries of non-English speaking countries too. The Prussian Instructions or the PIN code was designed in for the state public libraries of Germany in 1899. The code was designed as a guideline for the preparation of the union catalogue of the German public libraries and also libraries of many non-English speaking countries like Sweden, Norway, etc. (Sood, 2015). An English translation of the PIN-code was done by Andrew Osborn (1938).

Highlights of this Pre-1900 era Cataloguing:

The era of library cataloguing until 1900 was full of growth. The prime call at that time was for some rules or standards among the libraries, as libraries were following their local systems. This hindered the system from being known and used by limited persons only. A standard written rule was necessary for staff training as well as resource sharing purposes as legends like Jewett, Panizi have devised their rules aiming a union catalogue in mind.

3.2 From 1900 to 1950:

The era up to 1900 can be regarded as the birth of many standards for the cause of library cataloguing and the era after 1900 is known for modifications of such proposed models of standards. American Library Association (ALA) collaborating with the Library of Congress (LC) had donned the task of modification of standards up to a great extent in this period. ALA has introduced ***Condensed rules for an author and title catalogue***, prepared by its cooperation committee in 1883. However, major revision (ALA, 1902) to it was done for fixation of size, style of catalogue card and rules governing the entries in 1902. The revision was done under the newly formed ALA Advisory on Library Catalogue along with collaboration with LC. The modified ALA rules (1902) were loosely based on Cutter’s rule 1891 edition. The final version of the ALA Catalogue rules was published by Library of Congress (1949) in 1908 after the amalgamation of some rules from the British Library Association and these rules began to be known as the Anglo American Rules(AA rules). After the introduction, the Anglo American Rules were under criticism for being too elaborate and descriptive, tough to implement in small libraries. Hanson (1932), the chairman of the 1902 ALA advisory on Library Catalogue suggested about required modifications to the 1908 ALA rules and after discussion, a preliminary second edition of the ALA rules (ALA, 1941) was published in 1941. In this preliminary second edition, the code was divided into two parts, part I for Entry & Heading; part II for Description of Book. However, criticism of the ALA rules did not stop as the two-part catalogue of the new version was not able to cope up with required variations for different item types necessary in cataloguing (Tikku, 1983). Wishing to publish a more definitive version of the rules, ALA executive urged for a more detailed report from the ALA Division of Cataloguing & Classification which submitted their report (ALA, 1948) in 1948. ALA after consultation and revision, released some definitive rules under Part I of 1941 rules as the "Red Book" in 1949 while Library of Congress (1949) released a revised version of their practised rules of descriptive cataloguing as ***Rules for descriptive cataloguing in the Library of Congress*** in the same year. These rules were also known as the “Green Book.” In this period, intending to standardise the catalogue of serials, Library of Congress released ***Guide to the cataloguing of periodicals*** under the editorship of Mary Wilson (1918).

Ranganathan (1934) took an entirely different approach from the contemporary world trend of that time in cataloguing standard and introduced the Classified Catalogue Code in 1934. His work was entirely inspired by the subject approach for information and normative

principles. The “Canons of knowledge organisation” were the guiding rules for the code. Ranganathan’s approach was different and thought to be complete enough as a catalogue standard as it had both class-based arrangements of the catalogue along with an alphabetical index. Cross-reference entry was the main highlight of the Classified Catalogue Code. The logical arrangement of Ranganathan’s catalogue code is very significant in modern age also having evidence of its relation (Rajaram, 2013) to FRBR and its suitability for a modern-day computerised information system is also tested (Kashyap, 2002).

The highlight of this 1900-1950 period:

ALA and Library of Congress' collaboration post-1900 era provided the greater push needed for the development of catalogue standards. With the emergence of ideas of collaborative cataloguing and increased availability of variable item types in libraries in that era, the older cataloguing rules were felt inadequate. Library of Congress and ALA rules were aiming to cover up modern emerging trends for libraries post 1900 era in their cataloguing rules.

3.3 Post 1950 to Pre-Web era of cataloguing rules:

3.3.1 Lubetzky's vision:

The release of the Red Book of ALA and Green book of Library of Congress stirred controversy in the library community. Many praised the Library of Congress rules to be futuristic enough (Jolley, 1950; Osborn, 1950; Shera, 1950) terming the ALA rules as “going past time”. Ranganathan (1955) even though praised ALA for their effort, but termed their rule as lack of “organic unity in cataloguing elements”. Tikku (1983) in his review terms the era after 1950 as the era of “Code Revision Movement”. Because of the critical discussion made about the rules of Red and Green book, ALA Cataloguing and Classification Division requested LC for an intensive study about the rules and LC gave that duty to Seymour Lubetzky. Lubetzky (1953a) submitted his report discussing the need (Lubetzky, 1953b; Lubetzky, 1960) of “functionalism than formalism” in cataloguing rules. Lubetzky (1960) advocated for “objective specific rules”, that is based on “some basic but well-considered rules” so that the code remains “consistent in aim and method” that can meet the modern needs of cataloguers. Lubetzky's interest in the area proved to be the greatest moment in modern-day cataloguing history and his edited code (Lubetzky, 1960) later published as the ***Code of Cataloguing Rules; Author and Title Entry*** formed basis of the 12 statement Paris Principle (IFLA, 1961) at the International Conference on Cataloguing Principles at Paris in 1961. This Paris Principle later was followed for Anglo American Cataloguing Rules (AACR) in 1967.

3.3.2 Anglo American Cataloguing Rules(AACR):

The impact of Lubetzky’s (1953a) report on the comparative study of the existing cataloguing rules of ALA and LC is pioneering in bringing the “functionalism” principle in cataloguing codes. AACR was the big move towards a common cataloguing code across continents after the Paris principle (IFLA, 1961), bringing together ALA, Library Association of UK, LC and Canadian Library Association to work under a common floor. AACR was formed from the good of Panizi’s 91 rules, AA of 1908 and the ALA & Descriptive cataloguing rules of LC 1949. In its first version of 1967, AACR was released in two parts- one North American Text and one British text, as there were differences for corporate bodies entry in both the countries. AACR was suitable for card-based catalogue cards, and the visible difference was observed in AACR rules with the use of different punctuation marks for different access elements of documents, which were not that prominent in earlier rules.

3.3.3 AACR 1 Revision:

After the first conference in Paris in 1961, the International Meeting of Cataloguing Experts was held in 1969 at Copenhagen. IFLA (1977) introduced the prospect of International Standard Bibliographic Description (ISBD) as some guidelines for the creation of human-readable catalogues for describing a wide range of library items. ISBD was not a code, rather some statements on how a uniform standard can be achieved. ISBD didn't suggest what should be the entry point for a document in the catalogue but suggested how these should be arranged

(Svenonius, 2000). ISBD aimed (IFLA, 1977) "to produce a standard pattern that is recognisable to catalogue users and which enables the easy exchange of records created by different agencies".

The introduction of ISBD affected required modifications to the AACR of 1967. A Joint Steering Committee (JSC) was formed in 1974 having members from the stakeholders from AACR1 for the revision. Micheal Gorman & Paul W. Winkler from the British Library & Library of Congress respectively were appointed as editors by the JSC. AACR 2 was released in 1978 integrating the two versions of AACR 1 as a single edition in a two-part structure, part I (from chapter 1-13) for Description and part II (from chapter 21-26) for Headings, Uniform Titles and References. Chapter 14 to 20 were left blank for future update scope. Part I rules were inspired by ISBD and part II were loosely based on the Paris Principles code. No new version of AACR came up after the second edition but some revised versions in 1988, 1998 and 2002. AACR is a successful code and probably the most welcomed standard for card catalogues all over the world.

3.3.4 Machine Readable Cataloging (MARC): from catalogue rules towards Metadata

The era from the 1960s to the 1970s saw rapid growth in electronic file-based storage to the database management system, and the metadata concept was a relevant part of both the systems (Al-Khalifa & Davis, 2006). Even though libraries were dealing with various information access points of information resources in their cataloguing rules, but libraries never used the term metadata in cataloguing codes. Library of Congress was very much interested in the possibilities of the electronic storage of information and started looking for options that may help them to encode catalogue information in computer systems. With this aim, they started the LC MARC program at par with the rules based on AACR. Henriette Avram (1975) started designing the bibliographic data format for MARC in the 1960s at Library of Congress as a "protocol by which computers exchange, use and interpret bibliographic information". The push for MARC started (Seikel & Steele, 2011) as the discussion about the concept of library automation started in the 1950s. The MARC pilot project started in 1966 with the participation of 16 libraries, selected out of 40 libraries after a joint conference by LC, Council of Library Resources and Committee on Automation of the Association of Research Libraries in 1965. In 1968 the project was completed with 50000 MARC I records. LC as the nodal agency started the operational system for MARC in 1969 with a distribution of 1000 records per tape per week to US libraries. The project got so much interest that even before completion of MARC I, MARC II was introduced in 1967 at ALA's Midwinter conference (Seikel & Steele, 2011; Crawford, 1989). MARC II was more advanced than MARC I, and later MARC II went on to be the basis for Z39.5-1971 and ISO 2709-1973 standards. The designing of MARC was well structured to fit database structure with definitive content designators for different catalogue entry points, named as MARC Fields with their associated subfields named as MARC Tag and Indicators. Different modifications to MARC was done subsequently with time, imparting support for other materials and formats (Avram, 1975) like Maps & Serials (in 1970), Films (in 1971), Manuscripts (in 1973). The latest version of MARC is known as the MARC 21 which was formed merging the US MARC and UK MARC after an elaborate discussion from 1994 -1997 and finally released (Seikel & Steele, 2011) in 1999.

Highlights of post-1950 to the pre-web era

Seymour Lubetzky's vision for a functional catalogue for libraries is the great highlight of this era. Computerisation activities for cataloguing were realised in this period, and the Library of Congress' active participation for this computerisation movement resulted in the use of the word metadata for library catalogue rules, and MARC was a result of it. IFLA's ISBD inspired model resulted in the world's popular catalogue model AACR.

3.4 Library cataloguing post World Wide Web era:

3.4.1 MARC XML formats:

The idea of library automation post-1960s had a great impact on library cataloguing rules, and the term "metadata" was more commonly used than catalogues. Standards like MARC were suitable for database-driven information systems of bibliographic sources. With the emergence of the World Wide Web in the 1990s, libraries had to think of increased presence in the web environment. LC's Network Development and MARC standards office started the development of MARC Document Type Definition or MARC DTDs (Library of Congress, 2002) in 1995 as a "non-proprietary standard for text encoding so that machine-readable data could be exchanged between dissimilar text encoding environments". MARC as an ISO 2709 standard required DTD's so that relationships could be established with another data encoding standard ISO 8879. At initial state Standard Generalized Markup Language (SGML) was chosen as a framework for MARC DTDs and the first version was released in 1997. In 2000, same was released in eXtensible Markup Language (XML) and in 2002 MARC XML specifically for web environment was published.

3.4.2 Dublin Core initiative:

The combined effort of Ohio Computer Library Centre (OCLC) and National Center for Supercomputing Applications (NCSA) in 1995 resulted in a "generic" metadata schema named as Dublin Core suitable for describing a wide range of resources in an interoperable manner in the web (Weibel & Koch, 2000). Initiated as a small set of elements, the Dublin Core Metadata Initiative (2012) or simply DCMI quickly received the attention of the global community as a cross-domain standard currently recognised as ISO 15836. DCMI provided a 15 point element set suitable for describing any resource. With maturing of ideas like generic metadata model Resource Description Framework (RDF) at W3C, Dublin core vocabularies provided a contextual framework for the linked data and semantic web application movement. Dublin core later went on to become a full-fledged ontology for semantic web applications.

3.4.3 IFLA's modification to ISBD:

IFLA always wanted to have a standard in the cataloguing process for achieving better bibliographic control. ISBD (IFLA, 1977) provided a better prospect of control in the cataloguing rules in the 1970s, however in the changing environment of large scale database systems and connected world of web, ISBD had functional limitations. Realising the dramatic changes in library cooperation and cataloguing featured by the WWW, IFLA (1998) introduced the Functional Requirement for Bibliographic Records (FRBR) in 1998, not as a cataloguing rule like ISBD, but as an entity relationship-based data model for bibliographic control over connected systems. FRBR produced a WEMI (Work, Expression, Manifestation and Item) model suggesting declared relationships between these bibliographic entities. FRBR later inspired many design principles of ontologies for semantic web applications. IFLA later released Functional Requirements for Authority Data (FRAD) in 2009, Functional Requirements for Subject Authority Data (FRSAD) in 2011 as part of FRBR family of models. Denton (2007) opined "FRBR, as an endpoint of almost 175 years of thinking about what catalogues are for and how they should work-an endpoint, not the endpoint."

3.4.4 Updating AACR2

The required changes to AACR2 were made as revisions with times; however, in the maturing digital environment reflected in the libraries, the rules of descriptive cataloguing of AACR were insufficient to cope up. In 1997, the International Conference on the Principles & Future Development of AACR took place in Toronto, and the next year, IFLA released the FRBR rules. Work on the newer version of AACR, code-named as AACR3 started in 2002. Later the new code was named Resource Description and Access (RDA) and the Joint Steering Committee for AACR was renamed to RDA Joint Steering Committee (2009). Initially, FRBR was taken as base principle along with AACR2 rules, later FRAD rules also inspired the final version of RDA released in 2010 as "a new standard for descriptive cataloguing providing data elements, instructions and guidelines on recording the contents and formulating bibliographic metadata for description and access to information resources covering all types of content and media held in libraries and related cultural organisations such as museums and archives"

(Haider, 2019). The RDA text consisted of 10 sections in 37 chapters. RDA Toolkit is an online guideline service on RDA data. RDA worked as "a content standard" for modern-day web environment cataloguing and provides a package vocabulary for linked data applications via its entities, elements, relationship designators and controlled terms in RDF.

3.4.5 MARC's successor:

Library of Congress (2011) started working on the communication format BIBFRAME as a successor to MARC with an aim (Library of Congress, 2016a; Schreur, 2018) to "end libraries isolation from the semantic web". BIBFRAME proposed a model based on linked data with a view "to integrate with wider information community over the web" (Schreur, 2018) keeping the core value intact with libraries using the language of the semantic web. In BIBFRAME 1, four core levels of abstraction for a resource were defined as Work, Instance, Authorities and Annotations. However, the proposed model of BIBFRAME 1 had limitations regarding the neutrality of information as it combined the Work and Expression part of FRBR based on which RDA was developed; thus it became hard to combine RDA and BIBFRAME records (Schreur, 2018). Also incorporating comprehensive information of MARC records to BIBFRAME structure, the BIBFRAME 1 became less RDF compliant. Later in 2016, BIBFRAME2.0 model was proposed conversing the balance between the old records with the current best practices with the addition of other key concepts *viz.* Agents, Subjects and Events.

4 Landmarks in the Cataloguing Timeline:

From the review of the cataloguing history in four different time phases based on the objectives and functionalities of the proposed rules at different times, the major landmarks of these phases are

- the pre-1900 era: Important for a movement for written accepted catalogue codes or bibliographic cataloguing models across libraries.
- 1900 to 1950 era: The 1900 to 1950 era is known for greater collaboration between ALA, LC and British library associations for the development of the proposed cataloguing rules in the 1900 era.
- post-1950 to the pre-web era: Post-1950 era is vital for the development of two world-famous catalogue standards *viz.* AACR for card catalogue and MARC for computerised catalogue.
- Era after the World Wide Web(WWW): Post WWW era is known for the transition of metadata standards towards a more web-friendly environment and shifts towards linked data.

5 Mapping the philosophy of semantic web with modern Library catalogue:

Catalogue and cataloguing of resources are the two biggest enterprises in the robust history of library management. Catalogues were primary access points to library resources, and it comprises of information like author, title, subject, the language of the book, which are termed as metadata elements in the modern computing knowledge domain. Catalogues were designed for human use only, and therefore the attempts for standardisation of cataloguing rules were only meant for a global structured uniform format so that it remains uniform to understand for the readers across the globe. Changes in the rules and philosophy of cataloguing are only observed since libraries started to use computers and catalogues were not meant for human rather for computers. MARC is the first and most successful in this regard and has been a standard for database-driven computer storage. But most recent changes that have impacted libraries most is web technology. Libraries had to evolve newly to the online format and accordingly, libraries required standards that may help them to make the resources available in the online format. Catalogues were not limited to bibliographic control purpose but rather as a tool for providing services in the online format and the linear cataloguing code like MARC were not sufficient for this. Especially the web was also undergoing structural changes from the document-centric version of the 90's to a more social (Web2.0) and data-centric (semantic web and Linked Data) version where description and storage of information were more data-centric than document-oriented. Libraries had the advantage of having structured information

in the form of library catalogues, but it required actionable changes to make it work in the modern web environment.

5.1 What Semantic Web Proposed:

Sir Tim Berners Lee visions the modern web to be data-centric with added meaning to hyperlinks. Berners Lee, Hendler & Lassila (2001) stated: "the original web has conceptually been document-centric in which the links do not carry any semantics with them and when implemented with technical formats such as Hyper-Text Mark Up Language (HTML), the resultant web pages are more attuned to human consumption rather than machine processing." Linking and sharing of content are easy in the original version of the web, but documents needed human interventions to understand. The concept of linked data was forwarded by Berners Lee himself to harness the limitations where data will be connected to other data through URIs, and the connection will have some meanings which will be understandable for both machines and humans. The associated technologies that were put forwarded in support of linked data were RDF, RDFS, Ontology, SPARQL, etc. Instead of creating HTML documents on a particular topic in a particular knowledge domain, the information will be stored in a more logically structured manner in the form of ontologies which will comprise of some statements called triple. Ontologies will have specific vocabularies that will identify some distinct concepts (classes) in the knowledge domain, and those vocabularies will be connected by some relations, which will give them the associated meanings. Each entity under "Class", the relations will be uniquely identifiable by URIs. RDF, Web Ontology Language (OWL) are the languages to write ontologies for the semantic web.

Fig 1: Timeline of Library Metadata development history

5.2 What Modern Catalogue/Metadata standard proposed:

FRBR guideline of cataloguing proposed a hierarchical relationship-based approach for cataloguing an item. The WEMI model of FRBR (IFLA, 1998) can be realised as "Work as a concept of an idea which is Expressed (creation/performance) onto/into a physical or digital format aka Manifestation of which library has a copy (item)". Barbara Tillett (2005), chief of Cataloguing policy & support office of Library of Congress further gave a more structured view about the FRBR entities in three logical groups (in Fig 2), group 1 entities contains work, expression, manifestation or an item, group 2 entities are Person or Corporate bodies that are responsible for stewardship of group 1 entities and group 3 entities are concepts like event, time, subject, etc. which may further help in identification of group 1 entities. The continuum from Work to Expression; Expression to Manifestation further provides the addition of derivative relationships too for translations, editions, etc. The FRBR is related to a data model approach, as the ontologies for the semantic web. That is why FRBR became a useful guide for ontologies like CIDOC-CRM (Doerr, 2003), Music Ontology (Raimond, Abdallah, Sandler & Giasson, 2007) etc.

FRBR based RDA gives "a good example for the support of incorporating clustered information of the same records helping to show the different manifestations of a single work" (Tillett, 2005; Tillett, 2011). The Semantic web calls for a shared schema of knowledge domains with a controlled vocabulary of terms along with their relationship. RDA registry (2019) contains a list of RDA elements, relationship designators and controlled terminologies. RDA contains 13 classes viz. Entity, Work, Expression, Manifestation, Item, Agent, Collective Agent, Person, Family, Corporate Body, Nomen, Place, Timespan and have 12 groups of property items for each class entities till 2019. RDA graph is available to be downloaded in ontology frameworks like RDF, Turtle, N-triple, etc. The BIBFRAME 2.0 ontology (Library of Congress, 2016b) provides a more extensive vocabulary than RDA. The online BIBFRAME editor helps to convert standard MARC entries to BIBFRAME ontology. Table 1 gives an analogy of modern metadata standards to the requirements of the semantic web.

Table 1: Bridging semantic web philosophy to modern library metadata principles	
What Semantic web requires	What modern library metadata rules have
Knowledge representation should be logical and schema-based approach needed to fulfil the domain knowledge modelling.	FRBR guides the knowledge modelling of bibliographic sources in WEMI approach. BIBFRAME has its own modelling approach as Work, Item, Authorities and Annotations.
Ontology requires statements to be represented as subject, predicate and object.	RDA has its own vocabulary sets as Classes, properties to connect those classes to resources.
Vocabulary needs to be controlled and publicly mentionable with namespaces.	RDA element sets are build based on JSC study and accessible with the namespace http://rdaregistry.info/Elements/c/ . The namespace for BIBFRAME 2.0 is http://id.loc.gov/ontologies/bibframe/
RDF is a standard language for ontology creation.	RDA and BIBFRAME have its versions available in RDF, Turtle, n-Triple etc.

Fig 2: IFLA-FRBR conceptual model (Tillet, 2005)

6 Findings & Conclusion:

The cataloguing and metadata development for libraries has been a challenging task. The information resources of libraries have been changing with time from only print materials to different item types of information resources, and library cataloguing rules has to accommodate those changes in the catalogues of libraries. Later with computer and database systems, the catalogue had to adapt to the new computer environment. The rise of the web has created another challenge for libraries with the distributed form of similar information resources, and libraries had to cope up with these kinds of challenges too.

The current study makes an elaborate review of the cataloguing development history and how it changed to some renowned metadata standards with time. The modern metadata standards like RDA, FRBR, BIBFRAME are thought to be semantic web-ready. Even though there are criticisms (Baker, Coyle & Petiya, 2014) about RDA, FRBR etc. from time to time for being based on old catalogue rules like AACR, ISBD but in practice and actionable upgrades with time these standards have been able to incorporate all the requirements for modern semantic web-based information services. FRBR modelling approach is so suitable that it has inspired many large scale ontologies currently practised for collaborative knowledge creation and storage.

Library catalogue standards have undergone transitive changes from one form to another largely influenced by the changing work environment and different forms of resource availability in libraries. For surviving in the modern information age, the practical working structure of metadata for libraries had to change so that better information exchange among the libraries along with other knowledge creators is possible. Modern-day metadata standards are influenced by the opportunities provided by the World Wide Web towards libraries and works as a suitable base for data organisation at par with the semantic web standards. These will help the creation of large scale discovery services based on curated metadata of information resources and libraries have converted this challenge of the semantic web to opportunities with modern metadata standards.

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